

Practices of parents regarding sunlight exposure among their infants

(Public and Environmental Health)

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Introduction

Parental sunlight exposure practices are vital for infant health, supporting vitamin D synthesis, immunity, and overall well-being. While sunlight promotes bone health, excessive exposure increases risks like skin damage and cancer, necessitating a balance with protective measures.

Insufficient sunlight can cause vitamin D deficiency, leading to rickets, weakened immunity, and developmental issues. Parental knowledge, cultural beliefs, and socio-economic factors influence these practices, with misconceptions about skin darkening and cancer hindering proper exposure.

This study identifies sun exposure habits in Wah Cantt, a region with high literacy and parental employment. Despite awareness, challenges like time constraints and misinformation persist. Addressing these gaps can promote safer and more effective sun exposure for infants.

Aims & Objectives

To determine the parental practices regarding sunlight exposure among infants in Wah Cantt.

Methods

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: POF Hospital, Wah Cantt.

Study Duration: 4 months

Sample Size: 100

Sampling Technique: Convenient Sampling.

Sample Selection:

Inclusion Criteria: Parents (either father or mother) having infants whose age is between 1 months to 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria: Parents who are doctors or having severely ill children.

Data Collection Tool: A structured questionnaire was designed, covering demographic details (infant's age, gender, parental education, and employment) and sunlight exposure practices, including frequency, timing, duration, reasons for exposure, and concerns about risks.

Data Collection Procedure: Parents in pediatric OPD and wards were approached for consent, and the questionnaire was administered in an understandable language.

Data Analysis: Data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 21, with results presented in tables and charts for qualitative variables and the mean scores for quantitative variables.

Results

The mean age of infants in the study was 3.99 months with a standard deviation of 1.4 months.

A majority of respondents (67%) were unemployed, while 33% were employed.

79% of households had access to sunlight, while 21% reported limited or no direct sunlight exposure.

The gender distribution of infants was equal, with 50% male and 50% female.

81% of parents fully dressed their infants during sunlight exposure.

Only 35% parents reported using sunscreen to their infants during sunlight exposure

Conclusion

Overall, our study indicated good response on knowledge and awareness of sunlight exposure. Parents have good understanding on medical benefits of sunlight. However, parents need to break cultural stereotypes associated with sunlight exposure.

To promote safe sunlight exposure, awareness campaigns should address common misconceptions and emphasize balanced sun protection practices, including appropriate exposure timing and sunscreen use.

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Figure 4: Reasons for exposure to sunlight

Figure 3: Frequency of sunlight exposure

Figure 1: Regular exposure to sunlight

Figure 2: Time of sunlight exposure

